

Studies in Quinazolines. Part III: Synthesis of 2-Alkyl-3-Aralkyl-4-(3H) and 2-Mercapto-3-Aralkyl/alkyl-4(3H)-Quinazolinones

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In order to study physiological properties, several 2-alkyl-3-aralkyl and 2-mercapto-3-aralkyl/alkyl-4(3H) quinazolinones have been synthesized from the corresponding acylanthranilic acids and amines using either phosphoryl chloride or phosphorus trichloride, as a condensing agent.

Quinazoline derivatives show a wide variety of physiological activity such as antimalarial¹, antibacterial², diuretic³, hypnotic⁴, anticonvulsant⁵ and anticarcinogenic⁶. Bhargava and Ram⁷ have prepared some 3-substituted-2-mercapto 3-aryl-4-(3H)-quinazolinones as possible antimalarials. McCarty, Haines and Vanderwerf⁸ have also prepared 2-Alkylthio-3-aryl/alkyl-4-(3H) quinazolinones.

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With a view to study physiological properties of 2-alkyl-3-aralkyl (I) and 2-mercapto-3-aralkyl/alkyl/-4 (3H)-quinazolinones (II) they have been synthesized and reported in the present paper.

where $X = \text{H}, 6\text{-Br}, 6\text{-I}.$

Compounds (I) were synthesized through N-acyl anthranilic acids using phosphorus trichloride or phosphoryl chloride as condensing agent. Table I describes the compounds thus prepared. The experimental procedure was that due to J. Klosa⁹ with some modifications.

Compounds (II) were synthesized by condensation of anthranilic and 5-haloanthranilic acids with the corresponding isothiocyanates in absolute ethanol as described by Trivedi¹⁰. The products obtained were 2-thio-3-alkyl/aralkyl-2, 4-(1H, 3H)-quinazolinones. These on methylation with methyl iodide gave the corresponding 2-mercaptomethyl derivatives. Table II describes the compounds thus prepared.

All Compounds described in table I showed typical following absorption regions . 1695-1681 (N—C = O) and 1600-1581 (C = N) cm^{-1} .¹¹

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TABLE I
2, 3-Disubstituted-4 (3H)-Quinazolines

R_1	R_2	R_3	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis Found	% N Calcd.
CH ₃	H	2' -Cl	135-36	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O	9.2	9.3
"	"	3' -Cl	oil*	"	9.1	9.3
"	"	4' -Cl	78	"	9.2	9.3
"	"	2' -CH ₃	145	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	10.5	10.4
"	"	4' -Br	117	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O	8.0	8.1
"	"	3', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	134-35	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	10.1	10.1
"	"	2', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	140	"	10.0	10.1
"	"	2', 5'-(CH ₃) ₂	144	"	9.9	10.1
"	CH ₃	4' -Br	126	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O	7.7	7.8
"	CH ₃	4' -OCH ₃	138	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	9.4	9.5
C ₂ H ₅	H	2' -Cl	146	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O	8.7	8.8
"	"	3' -Cl	110	"	8.6	8.8
"	"	4' -Cl	125	"	8.7	8.8
"	"	3', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	80	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	9.5	9.6
"	"	2', 5'-(CH ₃) ₂	126	"	9.4	9.6

*Oil purified through a column *c* b.p. 135-48/3-5 mm.

Above compounds were crystallized from benzene or toluene.

TABLE II

No.	X	R_1	S-methyl derivative	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis			
						% N		% S	
						Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	H	H	—	246	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	10.2	10.4	11.9	12.0
"	"	"	S-methyl	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	9.7	9.9	11.7	11.8
2.	H	2' -Cl	—	262	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS	9.2	9.3	10.5	10.6
"	"	"	S-methyl	158	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	8.6	8.8	9.9	10.1
3.	H	3' -Cl	—	236	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS	9.2	9.3	10.4	10.6
"	"	"	S-methyl	98	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	8.7	8.8	10.0	10.1
4.	H	4' -Cl	—	230	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS	9.1	9.3	10.5	10.6
"	"	"	S-methyl	127	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	8.7	8.8	10.0	10.1
5.	H	2' -CH ₃	—	245	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	9.8	9.9	11.7	11.8
"	"	"	S-methyl	143	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	9.3	9.5	10.7	10.8
6.	H	3' -CH ₃	—	216	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	9.8	9.9	11.6	11.8
"	"	"	S-methyl	92	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS	9.3	9.5	10.6	10.8

TABLE II (Contd.)

7.	H	4'-CH ₃	—	258	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	9.8	9.9	11.7	11.8
	"	"	S-methyl	181	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	9.4	9.5	10.7	10.8
8.	H	4'-Br	—	220	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ OS	8.0	8.1	9.1	9.2
	"	"	S-methyl	114	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	7.6	7.8	8.8	8.9
9.	H	2', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	235	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS	9.3	9.5	10.7	10.8
	"	"	S-methyl	197	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.8	9.0	10.2	10.3
10.	H	2', 5'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	259-60	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	9.4	9.5	10.6	10.8
	"	"	S-methyl	167	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.9	9.0	10.1	10.3
11.	H	3', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	227	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	9.4	9.5	10.7	10.8
	"	"	S-methyl	109	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.8	9.0	10.2	10.3
12.	H	2-, 4'-(Cl) ₂	—	281	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	8.1	8.3	9.1	9.2
	"	"	S-methyl	122	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	7.8	8.0	8.7	8.8
13.	6-Br	H	—	231	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ OS	8.0	8.1	9.1	9.2
	"	"	S-methyl	138	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	7.6	7.8	8.7	8.9
14.	6-Br	2'-Cl	—	250	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrClN ₂ OS	7.1	7.3	8.3	8.4
	"	"	S-methyl	164	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrClN ₂ OS	6.9	7.1	8.0	8.1
15.	6-Br	3'-Cl	—	245-46	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrClN ₂ OS	7.1	7.3	8.2	8.4
	"	"	S-methyl	120	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrClN ₂ OS	7.0	7.1	7.9	8.1
16.	6-Br	4'-Cl	—	261-62	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrClN ₂ OS	7.2	7.3	8.2	8.4
	"	"	S-methyl	170	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrClN ₂ OS	6.9	7.1	8.0	8.1
17.	6-Br	2'-CH ₃	—	239	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	7.7	7.8	8.7	8.9
	"	"	S-methyl	165	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	7.3	7.5	8.3	8.5
18.	6-Br	3'-CH ₃	—	243	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	7.6	7.8	8.8	8.9
	"	"	S-methyl	100	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	7.4	7.5	8.4	8.5
19.	"	4'-CH ₂	—	257	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	7.7	7.8	8.8	8.9
	"	"	S-methyl	158	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	7.4	7.5	8.4	8.5
20.	4'-Br	4'Br	—	262	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ OS	6.4	6.6	7.4	7.5
	"	"	S-methyl	143	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₂ OS	6.3	6.4	7.2	7.3
21.	"	2', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	255	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	7.3	7.5	8.3	8.5
	"	"	S-methyl	114	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ OS	7.1	7.2	8.1	8.2
22.	"	2', 5'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	285	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	7.4	7.5	8.4	8.5
	"	"	S-methyl	150	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ OS	7.0	7.2	8.0	8.2
23.	"	3', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	254	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	7.4	7.5	8.3	8.5
	"	"	S-methyl	144	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ OS	7.0	7.2	8.1	8.2
24.	"	2', 4'-(Cl) ₂	—	295	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrCl ₂ N ₂ OS	6.7	6.7	7.5	7.7
	"	"	S-methyl	185	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrCl ₂ N ₂ OS	6.6	6.7	7.4	7.5
25.	6-I	H	—	238	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ IN ₂ OS	7.0	7.1	8.1	8.2
	"	"	S-methyl	140	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ IN ₂ OS	6.8	6.9	7.8	7.9
26.	"	2'-Cl	—	235	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClIN ₂ OS	6.4	6.5	7.4	7.5
	"	"	S-methyl	172	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClIN ₂ OS	6.2	6.3	7.1	7.2
27.	"	3'-Cl	—	228	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClIN ₂ OS	6.4	6.5	7.3	7.5

TABLE II (Contd.)

28.	„	S-methyl	170	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClIN ₂ OS	6.2	6.3	7.0	7.2
„	4'-Cl	—	238	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClIN ₂ OS	6.3	6.5	7.4	7.5
„	„	S-methyl	207	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClIN ₂ OS	6.2	6.3	7.1	7.2
29.	2'-CH ₃	—	290	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ IN ₂ OS	6.8	6.9	7.8	7.9
„	„	S-methyl	150	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ IN ₂ OS	6.4	6.6	7.5	7.6
30.	3'-CH ₃	—	235	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ IN ₂ OS	6.7	6.9	7.8	7.9
„	„	S-methyl	110	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ IN ₂ OS	6.5	6.6	7.5	7.6
31.	4'-CH ₃	—	257	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ IN ₂ OS	6.8	6.9	7.7	7.9
„	„	S-methyl	172	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ IN ₂ OS	6.4	6.6	7.4	7.6
32.	4'-Br	—	243	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrIN ₂ OS	5.9	5.9	6.7	6.8
„	„	S-methyl	124	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrIN ₂ OS	5.8	5.8	6.5	6.6
33.	2', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	275	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ IN ₂ OS	6.5	6.6	7.4	7.6
„	„	S-methyl	145	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	6.3	6.4	7.2	7.3
34.	2', 5'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	272	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ IN ₂ OS	6.5	6.6	7.5	7.6
„	„	S-methyl	147	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	6.3	6.4	7.1	7.3
35.	3', 4'-(CH ₃) ₂	—	240	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ IN ₂ OS	6.4	6.6	7.4	7.6
„	„	S-methyl	135	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	6.2	6.4	7.2	7.3
36.	2', 4'-(Cl) ₂	—	296	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ IN ₂ OS	6.1	6.2	6.8	6.9
„	„	S-methyl	210	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ IN ₂ OS	5.8	5.9	6.6	6.7

37.	6-Br	<i>n</i> -butyl	—	236	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	8.9	8.9	10.7	10.8
„	„	„	S-methyl	89	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	8.5	8.6	10.1	10.3
38.	„	<i>n</i> -amyl	—	198	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	8.5	8.6	10.2	10.3
„	„	„	S-methyl	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ OS	8.1	8.2	9.8	9.9
39.	„	<i>n</i> -hexyl	—	195-96	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ OS	8.2	8.2	9.8	9.9
„	„	„	S-methyl	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ OS	7.8	7.9	9.3	9.4
40.	„	cyclohexyl	—	194	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	8.2	8.3	9.7	9.9
„	„	„	S-methyl	could not be obtained in several attempts					

Note: 2-Thio compounds described in the above table were crystallised from ethanol, while their S-methyl thio derivatives were crystallised from acetone or methyl ethyl ketone.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Method for the Preparation of 2, 3-Disubstituted-4 (3H)-Quinazolinones using Phosphorus Trichloride as a condensing agent: Into a stirred mixture of *N*-acyl anthranilic acid (0.21 mole), toluene (250 ml) and amine (0.20 mole) is added a solution of phosphorus trichloride (9.2 g., 6.0 ml) in toluene (50 ml) during fifteen minutes and the mixture refluxed in an oil bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was treated with aqueous sodium carbonate and steam distilled to remove toluene. The solid obtained was washed with water, dried, and crystallised from benzene or toluene. Yield 50-55%.

Instead of phosphorus trichloride, when phosphoryl chloride was used as condensing agent, the process was essentially the same as described above.

General Method for the Synthesis of 2-Thio-3-alkyl/aralkyl-2, 4-(1 H, 3H)-Quinazoline-diones: A mixture of anthranilic acid or 5-haloanthranilic acid (0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol (40 ml) and isothiocyanate (0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) is refluxed on a waterbath for 2 hrs. In most of the cases the thioquinazolinones crystallised out during refluxing. In some cases the reaction mixture was heated for more than 2 hrs. The reaction mixture is cooled and the crystalline solid filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield 50 to 65%.

General Method for the Synthesis of S-methyl derivatives of Thioquinazolinones: A mixture of 2-thio-3-alkyl/aralkyl-2, 4 (1H, 3H) quinazoline dione (0.01 mole), anhydrous acetone (100 ml.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g) and methyl iodide (0.01 mole) was refluxed on a waterbath for 4 hrs. Most of the acetone was distilled out and the residue treated with water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from either acetone or methyl ethyl ketone.

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